

Primer: Software Containers for Reproducible Research

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Why containers enhance reproducibility

Sharing analytic code along with open data is often not sufficient to ensure the computational reproducibility¹ of research results. Computational results depend not only on the analytic software and third-party packages used, but also on additional software and underlying system components. When any of these dependencies receive updates or become unavailable, there is a risk that the analytic code cannot be executed anymore or produces results that differ from the original results.

Software containers can be a solution to this problem, as they provide a way to create a snapshot of the entire computing environment used in an analysis, including all system dependencies. Some use cases are re-running an old analysis, scaling up an existing analysis (e.g., increasing the sample size), running code in different operating systems or sharing an analysis pipeline including software and data. This primer introduces containerization concepts, workflows and platforms so that researchers with limited IT expertise or no access to dedicated staff can get started with improving the reproducibility of their computational analyses.

What are containers made of?

Containerization consists of three core elements ([The Turing Way Community, 2022](#)):

- **Recipe**
A human-readable and machine-readable text file which provides a blueprint of the entire computational environment used. It lists all required software components and dependencies.
- **Image**
A machine-readable file that assembles and stores all software components the recipe describes, that is, everything we need to run our analysis.
- **Container**
The container runs a working copy of the computing environment described in the recipe file and assembled in the image file. A container can be started and shut down, and it is meant to be temporary, unlike the container image.

Figure 1: The three components of containerization.

Containers are often compared with [Virtual Machines](#) ([The Turing Way Community, 2022](#)). In contrast to virtual machines, which contain a complete operating system, containers re-use parts of the operating system of the computing machine on which they run. Containers are therefore more lightweight and simpler than virtual machines, making them an easier to use and more practical tool for ensuring computational reproducibility in many moderately and even highly complex research settings.

¹Computational reproducibility is the ability of reported results to be reproduced by repeating the same computational steps on the original data ([Voelkl et al., 2023](#)). For an example of a systematic assessment of computational reproducibility in biomedical publications see [Samuel and Mietchen \(2024\)](#).

Workflows for using containers in scientific data analysis

Post-hoc containerization

In this scenario (see Figure 2) the analysis is initially conducted “as usual”, i.e. a computational environment is set up ad hoc by the researcher on their computer and then the analysis code is run. A basic requirement for computational reproducibility is the publication of the analytic code together with a list of the employed software packages and versions. A further step is to build a container, verify that the analysis can be re-run with identical results using that container and then publish the container recipe and image together with the analytic code.

Figure 2: Workflow of post-hoc containerization.

A priori containerization

In this scenario (see Figure 3) an analysis plan is defined and a containerized environment built from the start. This can happen either locally, on each analysts’ computers, or in a centralized manner, on a server. In both cases this approach has the advantage that all members of a research group work in the same environment and therefore can reliably run each other’s code to produce the same results. On the other hand, this setup requires some degree of coordination, and constrains all analysts to the same software choices. This latter challenge can be addressed by providing multiple containerized environments: one that is long-term stable and used e.g. for scientific publications, and a second one that is flexibly updated with recent or special software and can be used for more exploratory purposes.

Figure 3: Workflow of a priori containerization

Reusing recipes and images

For most purposes it is not necessary to write a container recipe from scratch. Instead an existing recipe or image can be re-used and adapted only slightly to contain the specific elements (e.g., libraries) needed for data analysis. There are many community-driven recipes and images for specific research fields or data analysis technology stacks (for example, based on R or Python). Table 2 in the section [Sharing container images](#) lists important registries and collections of such container images.

Software for building containers

Multiple software options are available for containerization, and the resulting fragmented landscape might be confusing. We provide a brief overview of the most popular software to build and manage containers in Table 1. In the following, this primer will focus primarily on using [Docker](#) as one of the most popular and longest running software for containerization.

Name	Description
Docker	Docker popularized container technology by providing easy-to-use packages for Linux, Windows and Mac operating systems. The Docker containerization technology is open-source and is developed by the homonymous company . Docker's basic functionality is free for non-commercial use in small organizations; otherwise it requires a paid subscription. <i>Limitations:</i> graphical applications are not easy to run in Docker containers and root user privileges are required to run containers. The latter means that it is difficult to run Docker containers for users that do not have administrator rights on their machine or cluster.
Podman	An open-source and free alternative to Docker, co-developed by engineers from the RedHat company and by a community of users. The Podman technology focuses more on security and simplicity and does not rely on administrator rights (root privileges), but otherwise is quite similar to the Docker technology.
Singularity	Singularity is intended to be easy to set up and to run on high performance computing (HPC) machines or clusters with multiple users. It is developed with a data science focus by Sylabs . Graphical applications can run inside a container, and users do not need special permissions to run an image. Singularity is available in an open-source community-driven edition, SingularityCE .
Apptainer	Apptainer is the name of a fork of the Singularity project that moved from the control of a single company to the Linux Foundation (see this announcement from 2021). Both Sylab's Singularity and Apptainer continue to be developed and from the user perspective they should remain compatible for the foreseeable future.

Table 1: Platforms for containerization that can be useful for computational reproducibility.

Sharing container images

There are a number of useful platforms that facilitate the process of building, sharing and integrating containers into the scientific workflow. They use the technology for building containers described above but make it easier for researchers to store and share their container images, set up new containers or run existing containers.

Name	Description
Docker Hub	A very large Docker container registry. Users with a free account can register multiple public container images and only one private repository.
GitHub Container Registry	A very large Docker and Singularity container registry to store images and associate them with version controlled repositories at GitHub . Users with a free account can register multiple public container images.
GitLab Container Registry	A container registry of GitLab , a hosting service for version controlled repositories. Container images in the registry can be kept private and are available in the free tier.
Neurodesk	Free platform that allows to setup a plug-and-play, browser-accessible, containerized data analysis environment. It offers containers (currently with software applications for neuroscience) as well as computing resources to run them. It is very easy to use without requiring advanced programming skills or difficult software installations.
Renku	This platform developed by the Swiss Data Science Center helps researchers bringing code, computations and data in one place, creating a sort of a project or lab dashboard that can be managed in the browser and easily shared privately or publicly. It provides containers with pre-installed software frequently used in research. Its free tier offers also minimal computing resources that would allow to run containers from the browser, with paid options to increase these resources.
Rocker	A project that provides Docker container images with different versions of the statistical programming language R and pre-installed libraries optimized for different purposes (Boettiger and Edelbuettel, 2017). A number of R packages and other tools are built to support steps up- and down-stream from using Rocker images; they are referred to as the "Rockerverse" (Nüst et al., 2020a).

Table 2: Platforms that facilitate sharing and using software containers in research.

Simple example to get started

Running a container can be surprisingly easy. Here is a minimal example to run a container from one of the images in the Rocker project on a user's computer. In this example we assume that [Docker Desktop](#) is installed and the user has administrator rights. This workflow reuses (see [Reusing recipes and images](#)) an existing container image from the Rocker project, so we just need to download it and run the container. This can be done with the following command in the *terminal* (in Windows and MacOS the Docker Desktop application needs to be running):

```
docker run -p 8787:8787 -e PASSWORD=mypassword rocker/rstudio:4.4.1
```

This starts a self-contained computing environment running RStudio and R version 4.4.1. It can be accessed in a internet browser at `localhost:8787`. The login credentials are `rstudio` as username and `mypassword` as password (the password can be set differently by changing the string in the command above). This environment is now running *within* a container on the user's computer (called the 'host'). By default it cannot access any data outside the container. The container can be given access to (re-search) data on the host machine using [Docker volumes](#). In the given example, adding the option `-v <path-to-data>:/home/rstudio` mounts the given path in the container, i.e., it makes that directory accessible from the container. Note that the container will be running until it is stopped, e.g. by typing Ctrl + C in the terminal.

Summary

Software containerization can improve computational reproducibility. A rich ecosystem of tools facilitates containerization for researchers, irrespective of their technical expertise. We encourage scientists getting started with containerization to start by reusing available containers, and to then gradually incorporate containerization into their routine analysis and publication workflows.

Additional resources

We recommend the following materials for additional reading on this topic.

Courses and documentation

- [Official Docker documentation - getting started](#)
- [Official Docker documentation - use cases](#)
- [Course from *The Carpentries*: Introduction to Docker](#)
- [Chapter on Docker from *The Turing Way* handbook](#)

Reports

- A practical technical report with 10 simple rules for writing Docker files (i.e., container recipes for Docker) for reproducible data science ([Nüst et al., 2020b](#)).
- A detailed report with more in-depth practical examples from psychological research ([Wiebels and Moreau, 2021](#)).
- A more extensive report on using containers with version control, dependency management and dynamic document generation ([Peikert and Brandmaier, 2021](#)).

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